

Master in Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Transformer neural network architecture for codec-based unconditional and conditional environmental sound synthesis

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Supervisor: Lonce Wyse

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Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Motivation	1
1.2	Objectives	1
1.3	Procedural Audio	2
1.4	Approach	2
2	Neural Discrete Latent Representations	4
2.1	Introduction	4
2.2	Vector-Quantized Variational Autoencoder	5
2.3	Residual Vector-Quantized VAE	6
2.4	Descript Audio Codec (Improved RVQGAN)	7
3	Transformer Neural Network	8
3.1	Introduction	8
3.2	Transformer Neural Network Architecture	9
3.2.1	Sequence-to-sequence	10
3.2.2	Decoder-only	10
3.2.3	Encoder-only	10
3.3	Embeddings	11
3.3.1	Sinusoidal Positional Encoding	12
3.3.2	Learned Positional Encoding	12
3.3.3	Rotary Positional Encoding	13
3.4	Multi-Head Self-Attention Mechanism	14

4	Codec-based Audio Language Modeling	15
4.1	Jukebox	16
4.2	MusicGen	17
4.3	UniAudio	18
5	Data and Methodology	20
5.1	Datasets	20
5.1.1	"Footsteps" Dataset	20
5.1.2	"Bees", "Wind", "Pistons", "Applause" Dataset	21
5.2	Dataset Tokenization	21
5.3	Generation Strategy	23
5.4	Conditioning Strategies	24
5.4.1	Unconditional Synthesis	25
5.4.2	"One-hot embedding injection" Conditioning	25
5.4.3	"Continuous value embedding injection" Conditioning	26
5.4.4	"Control Codes Injection" Conditioning	28
6	Experiments and Results	29
6.1	Models and Hyperparameters	29
6.2	Training	30
6.3	Quantitative Analysis	31
6.4	Qualitative Analysis	32
7	Discussion and Conclusion	34
7.1	Interpretation of the Results	34
7.2	Future Work	36
	List of Figures	37
	Bibliography	39

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Abstract

This thesis investigates strategies to overcome the limitations of Neural Audio Synthesis (NAS) approaches in procedural audio, with a particular focus on enhancing conditional synthesis techniques. Contrary to previous assertions regarding limited control over meaningful conditioning parameters in neural approaches, we show that codec-based audio language modeling is a promising approach for procedural audio, both for its conditioning possibilities and the high quality of the sounds it produces. We concentrate on "environmental sounds", an underexplored area in neural audio synthesis, utilizing five distinct datasets of contact and texture sounds. The methodology employs the Improved RVQGAN neural audio compression codec (Descript Audio Codec) to compress audio waveforms into hierarchical sequences of discrete latent representations, thereby enabling the use of autoregressive Transformer models for sequence modeling. A total of 64 autoregressive decoder-only Transformer neural networks were trained using three different conditioning strategies, as well as unconditional synthesis. Finally, we report a comprehensive quantitative and qualitative analysis of these models.

Keywords: Transformer Neural Network; Audio Language Modeling; Procedural audio; Environmental Sound Synthesis; Conditional Sound Generation

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

In recent years, procedural audio has gained popularity in various fields, including sound design, virtual environments, automotive industry, and video game development. A comprehensive review of the state of the art in procedural audio has highlighted the emerging potential of neural audio synthesis (NAS) in this field, particularly noting its capacity to produce sounds of exceptionally high quality compared to other generative audio techniques [1].

However, as reported by the review, current Neural Audio Synthesis (NAS) approaches face limitations in their applicability to procedural audio due to restricted control capabilities. This constraint presents a significant research opportunity to enhance the functionality and versatility of NAS in procedural audio contexts.

1.2 Objectives

The primary aim of this research work is to show how codec-based audio language modeling through autoregressive Transformer architecture, represents a promising avenue for advancing procedural audio. We posit that this approach offers potential advantages in both conditioning capabilities and the quality of generated sounds.

Furthermore, this research addresses a notable gap in the existing literature. While codec-based audio language modeling via Transformer architectures has demonstrated outstanding audio quality for music and speech in recent years, prior studies [2][3][4] have identified the need for expanded research on "environmental sounds" - defined as non-speech, non-music audio. This thesis will concentrate exclusively on models pertaining to the "environmental sounds" category, thereby contributing to an underexplored area within the field of neural audio synthesis.

1.3 Procedural Audio

According to the review [1], procedural audio is defined as real-time audio generation "from scratch" with dynamic adaptation to changing inputs via meaningful parameters. "From scratch" constraint explicitly excludes sample-based techniques such as granular synthesis, concatenative synthesis [5], and any "processed recording" method, distinguishing it from the broader field of "procedural sound design".

A critical aspect of procedural audio is the use of "meaningful parameters" that correlate strongly with the physical mechanisms of sound generation, offering intuitive control beyond basic perceptual mappings like spectral centroid to brightness or RMS to loudness. Current neural audio models, exemplified by RAVE [6], while capable of real-time generation, are limited by their reliance on abstract conditioning parameters, which fall short of the "meaningful" control required in procedural audio.

1.4 Approach

We used five distinct datasets of contact sounds and texture sounds: "Footsteps" (28,000 sound files in 28 categories), and "Bees", "Pistons", "Wind", and "Applause" (each comprising 6,300 sound files with 21 classes of conditioning generation parameters). Among the relevant articles considered in the state-of-the-art review [1], the taxonomy of "contact sounds" is the most relevant based on the number of citations and percentage of instances. Other relevant taxonomies in the review

belong to the category of "texture sounds."

We employ the Improved RVQGAN neural audio compression codec (Descript Audio Codec) [7], which compresses audio waveforms into sequences of hierarchical latent codes while preserving temporal integrity. This compression allows us to model the audio as sequences, facilitating the use of Transformer models.

Our approach involves training decoder-only autoregressive Transformer language models on these neural discrete latent representations (latent audio tokens) in order to predict sequences. The predicted latent representation sequences are then decoded back into audio waveforms using the Descript Audio Codec decoder. Given the real-time requirements of procedural audio generation, this study places particular emphasis on the trade-off between audio quality and inference time.

Chapter 2

Neural Discrete Latent Representations

2.1 Introduction

The goal of neural generative audio models is to learn the underlying structure in the data in an unsupervised fashion and generate new data with the same statistical properties that is diverse in its outputs. A challenge in generative audio is to have an efficient model despite the high-dimensionality of audio data at industry-standard sample rates. Such models need to represent structures at different time-scales in order to generate high-quality audio with long-term consistency.

In recent years, compressing audio data into discrete latent representations through neural codecs and performing language modeling tasks has shown to be an effective approach. State-of-the-art autoregressive generative audio systems such as MusicLM [8], MusicGen [2], and UniAudio [9] use residual vector-quantization neural audio codecs to convert audio into a sequence of discrete tokens suitable for sequence modeling by autoregressive Transformer models. The quality of the output of a generative model based on language modeling on discrete latent tokens depends strongly on the quality of its respective codec algorithm.

2.2 Vector-Quantized Variational Autoencoder

State-of-the-art neural audio codecs use Vector-Quantized Variational Auto-Encoder (VQ-VAE) [10] as a fundamental building block due to its ability to learn arbitrarily complex distributions in audio data in an unsupervised fashion. It has been shown that the type of vector quantization algorithm, the use of Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) architectures [11], and other strategies play a fundamental role in optimizing the quality and efficiency of data compression. VQ-VAE, first introduced by the Google DeepMind team in 2017, combines the strengths of vector quantization and variational autoencoders to create a powerful framework for learning discrete latent representations.

Vector Quantization (VQ) is a technique that maps high-dimensional vectors to a finite set of code vectors. Let $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ be an input vector, and $\mathcal{C} = \{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \dots, \mathbf{e}_K\}$ be a codebook containing K code vectors, where $\mathbf{e}_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, K$. The quantization operation $Q(\mathbf{x})$ maps the input vector x to the nearest code vector in the codebook. $Q(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{e}_k$, where $k = \arg \min_i \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{e}_i\|^2$, $\|\cdot\|$ is the Euclidean norm. The quantization error r , also referred to as the residual, is defined as the difference between the input vector and its quantized representation: $r = \mathbf{x} - Q(\mathbf{x})$. The codebook is typically learned by minimizing the average quantization error over a training dataset \mathcal{D} :

$$\min_{\mathbf{e}_1, \dots, \mathbf{e}_K} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x} \sim \mathcal{D}} [\|\mathbf{x} - Q(\mathbf{x})\|^2] \quad (2.1)$$

Figure 1: VQ-VAE vector quantization process from [10].

2.3 Residual Vector-Quantized VAE

State-of-the-art Variational Autoencoder (VAE) codecs implementing Residual Vector Quantization (RVQ), such as SoundStream [12] and EnCodec [13], have shown outstanding performance at low bitrates. A significant improvement in recent RVQ-VAE models is the concept of bitrate scalability, where a single model can output at different bitrates. This variation in the Vector Quantization technique, compared to the original VQ-VAE, was first introduced in 2019 [14] and has been particularly relevant in the development of neural audio codecs.

Residual Vector Quantization (RVQ) works through iterative refinement. It begins by encoding the input vector x with an initial quantizer q_1 . Then, it calculates the residual r_1 , the difference between the original vector and its quantized version. This residual becomes input for the next quantization stage q_2 . The process repeats across multiple stages, each stage quantizing the residual from the previous stage. This iterative approach allows RVQ to progressively capture finer details, resulting in a more accurate representation of the original vector x .

$$\mathbf{x} \approx \mathbf{q}_1(\mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{q}_2(\mathbf{r}_1) + \mathbf{q}_3(\mathbf{r}_2) + \cdots + \mathbf{q}_K(\mathbf{r}_{K-1}) \quad (2.2)$$

Figure 2: EnCodec architecture from [13].

2.4 Descript Audio Codec (Improved RVQGAN)

The Improved Residual Vector-Quantized Generative Adversarial Network (RVQGAN) [7] model enhances the EnCodec and SoundStream algorithms through two main factors: advanced vector quantization techniques inspired by the image domain [15] and refined adversarial and reconstruction losses. The model improves codebook learning techniques by preventing unused codebooks and addressing the side-effect of quantizer dropout, which previously compromised full-bandwidth audio quality.

The design also incorporates minor variations in losses and discriminator architecture, enabling the model to perform well across various sound types. However, like other GAN-based generation models, SoundStream and EnCodec models suffer from audio artifacts such as tonal distortions, pitch inconsistencies, and periodicity issues. To mitigate these problems, the ReLU activation function is replaced with the Snake activation function. This substitution is particularly effective because humans are highly sensitive to periodicities and regular patterns in audio signals, making such artifacts easily detectable. A general Snake function can be formulated as: $\text{snake}(x) = x + \frac{1}{\alpha} \sin^2(\alpha x)$.

EnCodec and SoundStream algorithms imperfectly model high frequencies, leading to audio that is clearly distinguishable from the originals. These algorithms are often tailored to specific types of audio signals, such as speech or music, and struggle to model generic sounds. In contrast, the DAC codec demonstrates minimal loss in quality, fewer artifacts, and higher compression rates. Additionally, it proves to be universal, performing exceptionally well on all types of audio signals.

Chapter 3

Transformer Neural Network

3.1 Introduction

The Transformer architecture, first proposed in 2017 [3], marked a remarkable step forward in the field of deep learning. This architecture has dominated sequence modeling in recent years due to its ability to fully capture relationships within a given sequence. Transformers have shown state-of-the-art performance in natural language processing and have since expanded into various artificial intelligence domains, including protein sequences [16], [17], [18], [18] vision [19], and audio generation.

The Transformer's predecessor, the Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) [20], made significant advancements in areas such as natural language processing and speech recognition. However, during back-propagation suffered from two problems: vanishing and exploding gradients [21]. Although the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Network [22], a particular type of RNN, addressed some issues, the vanishing gradient problem persisted. This problem results in the model "forgetting" information from the earliest timepoints in the sequence.

The Transformer architecture has shown to overcome these problems, since each element in a sequence attends to all other elements in the sequence. Self-attention mechanism allows the model to consider the entire input sequence when computing the representation of each element, however, at the cost of high computational

complexity.

The Transformer neural network has overcome these problems through a mechanism called self-attention, which allows each element in a sequence to attend to all other elements. This self-attention mechanism enables the model to consider the entire input sequence when computing the representation of each element, albeit at the cost of increased computational complexity.

3.2 Transformer Neural Network Architecture

The Transformer architecture, introduced by Vaswani et al. (2017) in their seminal paper "Attention is All You Need" [3], comprises two primary components: the encoder and the decoder. Both are composed of stacks of identical layers.

Figure 3: Transformer architecture from [3].

Each encoder layer consists of two main sub-layers: a multi-head self-attention mechanism and a position-wise fully connected feed-forward network. The self-attention mechanism enables the model to focus on different parts of the input sequence simultaneously, capturing dependencies regardless of distance. The feed-forward network, applied independently to each position, further processes the information extracted

by the self-attention mechanism.

Decoder layers incorporate an additional mechanism called look-ahead masking, which prevents positions from attending to subsequent positions. This ensures that the prediction for a given position depends only on preceding outputs, maintaining causality. The decoder also includes a multi-head attention mechanism that attends to the encoder's output (cross-attention). Both encoder and decoder layers utilize residual connections and layer normalization to facilitate training and enhance performance.

Over time, variations of the Transformer have been developed to cater to specific needs. We can divide these variations into three macro-groups: sequence-to-sequence (encoder-decoder), decoder-only, and encoder-only Transformers.

3.2.1 Sequence-to-sequence

The original Transformer model is designed as a "sequence-to-sequence" architecture, consisting of an encoder and a decoder. The encoder processes the input sequence and generates a contextualized representation, while the decoder generates the output sequence based on the encoder's representation and its own previous outputs. This architecture is particularly effective for tasks such as machine translation.

3.2.2 Decoder-only

The encoder-only Transformer, exemplified by models like BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) [23], focuses solely on the encoding mechanism to produce context-aware representations of the input text, making it highly effective for tasks such as text classification and named entity recognition.

3.2.3 Encoder-only

On the other hand, the decoder-only Transformer, used in models like GPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer) [24] or LLaMA [25], employs only the decoding

mechanism to generate text, which is particularly suited for language modeling and text generation tasks.

3.3 Embeddings

Transformer architecture takes embedded vectors (embeddings) as input. Tokenization and embeddings are critical steps in preparing audio for input into the Transformer model. Tokenization in Natural Language Processing (NLP) involves breaking down the text into smaller units, typically words or subwords, known as tokens. To each token is associated a unique ID in a vocabulary. A vocabulary is the set of all possible unique IDs.

Let X and Y be mathematical objects. We say that X is embedded in Y if there exists an injective and structure-preserving map $f : X \rightarrow Y$. The map f is called an embedding of X into Y . The embedding mapping typically performed in Large Language Models (LLMs) is a simple lookup operation in a weight matrix. LLMs embeddings are high dimensional dense vectors, capturing syntactic and semantic information, and enabling efficient and meaningful input for neural network models.

Figure 4: Token embedding mechanism representation.

Before the multi-head self-attention mechanism, the embedding vectors are positionally encoded. Positional encoding is a crucial component in Transformer architectures, addressing the model's inherent inability to capture sequential information. Three prominent approaches have emerged: sinusoidal, learned, and rotary positional encoding (RoPE).

3.3.1 Sinusoidal Positional Encoding

Sinusoidal positional encoding is calculated using a geometric progression of frequencies, where the frequency of the sine and cosine functions increases exponentially as the position in the embeddings sequence increases, and decreases relative to the index of the feature in the embedding vector. It can be mathematically formulated as:

$$PE_{(pos,2i)} = \sin(pos/10000^{2i/d_{model}}), PE_{(pos,2i+1)} = \cos(pos/10000^{2i/d_{model}}) \quad (3.1)$$

This allows the model to easily learn to attend by relative positions, since for any fixed offset k , PE_{pos+k} can be represented as a linear function of PE_{pos} . The positional vectors resulting from this formula are vectors of the same dimensionality as the embedding vectors, and are summed to them.

3.3.2 Learned Positional Encoding

Learned positional encoding, treats position embeddings as trainable parameters, potentially capturing more nuanced positional relationships. The resulting matrix of learned positional encoding can be represented as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \cdots & a_{1d_{model}} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \cdots & a_{2d_{model}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{length_{seq}1} & a_{length_{seq}2} & \cdots & a_{length_{seq}d_{model}} \end{bmatrix}$$

E_{pos} is a learned embedding vector $(a_1 \ a_2 \ \cdots \ a_{d_{model}})$ for position pos , where $length_{seq}$ is the maximum pos value. In this approach, each position is associated with a learnable vector of the same dimension as the token embeddings. These

vectors are initialized randomly and updated during training. The model learns to associate specific patterns in these vectors with positional information. As with sinusoidal embeddings, the matrix of positional vectors has the same shape as the sequence of embedding vectors and is summed with them.

3.3.3 Rotary Positional Encoding

RoPE [26] applies a rotation to the token embeddings. For a complex-valued token embedding $X = a + bi$, the rotated embedding is:

$$X_{rot} = X e^{i\theta_m}$$

$\theta_m = f(m, d)$ is a function that computes the rotation angle based on the position m and dimension d . A common choice for f is:

$$\theta_m = \frac{m}{10000^{2d/D}}$$

D is the total dimension of the embedding. In practice, for real-valued embeddings, this rotation is applied to pairs of dimensions $(2i, 2i + 1)$:

$$\begin{bmatrix} X_{2i} & X_{2i+1} \end{bmatrix} rot = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_m & -\sin \theta_m \\ \sin \theta_m & \cos \theta_m \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X_{2i} & X_{2i+1} \end{bmatrix}$$

RoPE encodes positional information by rotating the existing token embeddings in the complex plane. This rotation preserves the norm of the embeddings while encoding relative position information. The key advantage of RoPE is that it allows the attention mechanism to directly capture relative positional information without additional parameters or operations. The multiplicative nature of the interaction makes RoPE learn the joint relation between the embedding and the specific position. In general, additive interactions are more natural for applications that are less strongly dependent on the joint values of two components, like feature aggregation or feature detection or, in this case, sinusoidal and learned positional embeddings.

3.4 Multi-Head Self-Attention Mechanism

The multi-headed self-attention mechanism, a cornerstone of the Transformer architecture, operates on an input sequence $X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d_{model}}$, where n is the sequence length and d_{model} is the embedding dimension. Each embedding vector is divided into multiple vectors called “transformer heads”. For each attention head $i \in \{1, \dots, h\}$, where h is the number of heads, three linear projections are applied to create queries $Q_i = XW_i^Q$, keys $K_i = XW_i^K$, and values $V_i = XW_i^V$, where $W_i^Q, W_i^K, W_i^V \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{model} \times d_k}$ are learnable parameter matrices and $d_k = d_{model}/h$ is the dimension of each head. The attention scores for each head are computed as $A_i = \text{softmax}(\frac{Q_i K_i^T}{\sqrt{d_k}})$, where the scaling factor $\sqrt{d_k}$ prevents excessive magnitudes in the dot products. The output of each attention head is then calculated as $H_i = A_i V_i$. Finally, the outputs from all heads are concatenated and linearly projected to produce the final output: $\text{MultiHead}(X) = \text{Concat}(H_1, \dots, H_h)W^O$, where $W^O \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ is another learnable parameter matrix. This mechanism allows the model to jointly attend to information from different representation subspaces at different positions, significantly enhancing its ability to capture complex dependencies within the input sequence.

Figure 5: Self-attention mechanism representation for one head.

Chapter 4

Codec-based Audio Language Modeling

The multi-headed self-attention block of the Transformer architecture scales quadratically in terms of both computational and memory constraints, thereby reducing its effectiveness for very long sequences (as is the case with raw audio at industry standard sampling rates) and resulting in very slow inference speed. Combining Transformer language models (LMs) with learned discrete audio tokens resulting from neural audio codecs has been shown to be the common strategy for all state-of-the-art autoregressive generative audio models in recent years.

Figure 6: Fig. 1. Timeline of current neural codec models and codec-based audio language models from [27].

4.1 Jukebox

Jukebox [28] by OpenAI trains an autoregressive Transformer over the compressed discrete latent tokens of a VQ-VAE-2 model. The model adopts a hierarchical approach to generate tokens at various temporal resolutions which are later combined to reconstruct raw waveforms. The lowest temporal resolution encapsulates the most important components of the audio whereas the higher temporal resolutions encode fine-grained information. The target of the model is music with singing, the generation is conditioned by text inputs. After training VQ-VAE-2, the authors

Figure 7: JukeBox encoding, decoding and RVQ process from the original paper [28].

model distribution in the following way:

$$p(z) = p(z^{\text{top}}, z^{\text{middle}}, z^{\text{bottom}}) = p(z^{\text{top}})p(z^{\text{middle}}|z^{\text{top}})p(z^{\text{bottom}}|z^{\text{middle}}, z^{\text{top}})$$

The prior $p(z)$ is split up into a top-level prior $p(z^{\text{top}})$, which feeds into two up-samplers, namely $p(z^{\text{middle}})$ and $p(z^{\text{bottom}})$. The conditioning flows in a hierarchical structure. Each lower level has access to the information from the level(s) above it. The conditioning information consists of a variety of information, such as artist and genre labels as well as a timing signal indicating the duration of the music piece.

4.2 MusicGen

MusicGen [2] by Meta is an autoregressive single-stage Transformer decoder-only language model for 32 kHz music generation conditioned on text prompt and melody. The model operates over residual discrete tokens streams from low bit-rate EnCodec neural codecs, leveraging the internal structure of the quantized audio tokens using different interleaving mechanism, eliminating the need for a cascade of Transformers of the Jukebox model.

Let $X \in \mathbb{R}^{d \cdot f_s}$ be the reference audio random variable, where d is the audio duration in seconds and f_s is the sample rate. X is encoded in a lower frame rate $f_r \ll f_s$, that is quantized via RVQ into $Q \in \{1, \dots, N\}^{K \times d \cdot f_r}$, where N is the codebook size and K represents the number of codebooks. MusicGen incorporates arbitrary codebook interleaving patterns. Let us denote $\Omega = \{(t, k) : t \in \{1, \dots, d \cdot f_r\}, k \in \{1, \dots, K\}\}$ as the set of (t, k) time-step/codebook pairs and P_s as a particular pattern for time-step s .

Figure 8: MusicGen different codebook interleaving patterns from the original paper [2].

The interleaving mechanism, plays a significant role in the performance of the model, heavily influencing the inference time and the sound quality. It has been shown that

the flattening pattern achieves the best quality of sound but is the slower pattern at inference while with the parallel pattern has been shown the opposite result.

Recently, different research highlighted possible strategies to improve existing generative audio models, for example [29] proposes a codebook pattern decoding strategy that leads to a significantly faster generation speed and close to the “flat pattern” which is the higher quality approach but at the cost of very slow inference speed.

Figure 9: Stack and delay codebook pattern from [29].

4.3 UniAudio

UniAudio system [9] is a universal audio generation state-of-the-art 1B parameters model trained on 165K hours of audio data that leverages Large Language Model (LLM) techniques and to generate multiple types of audio and handle a variety of generative tasks. The model demonstrates unprecedented versatility by successfully addressing eleven distinct audio generation tasks within a single unified framework. These tasks span a wide range of applications: Text-to-Speech (TTS), Voice Conversion (VC), Speech Enhancement (SE), Target Speaker Extraction (TSE), Singing Voice Synthesis (SVS), Text-to-Sound, text-to-music, audio and speech editing, speech de-reverberation, instructed TTS. The model achieves state-of-the-art or competitive results on most of the 11 audio generation tasks All audio types and input modalities are tokenized into discrete sequences using a custom-built neural

audio codec based on the EnCodec RVQ framework, but with significant modifications to make it more suitable for universal audio generation tasks. All tasks in the model are formulated as sequential modeling problems, with input conditions and target audio concatenated into a single sequence. Long sequences from audio tokenization can be handled by the proposed Multi-Scale Transformer, a novel architecture to handle long sequences from audio tokenization, consisting of a “Global Transformer” for inter-frame correlations, and a “Local Transformer” for intra-frame correlations.

Figure 10: Multi-Scale Transformer representation from [9]. $\langle e \rangle$ represent the end of the sequence. z_t^k denotes the k-th audio token at t-th frame.

Chapter 5

Data and Methodology

5.1 Datasets

Five different datasets of 44,100 Hz audio files were used: "Footsteps", "Bees", "Pistons", "Wind", and "Applause". The "Footsteps" dataset comprised 28,000 sounds, each 7 seconds long, generated through an algorithm from 28 sounds of irregular rate footsteps taken from Freesound (<https://freesound.org/>), the ESC-50 dataset [30], and ZapSplat (<https://www.zapsplat.com/>). The datasets for "Bees", "Pistons", "Wind", and "Applause" were generated by "Syntex: parametric audio texture datasets for conditional training of instrumental interfaces" [31]. Syntex was a collection of dataset generators and a database of parameterized audio textures. It also included a suite of tools for creating and labeling datasets designed for training and testing generative neural networks for parametrically conditioned sound synthesis. Each of these datasets consisted of 6,300 sounds, each 6 seconds long. The conditioning values in the texture datasets ranged from 0.0 to 1.0, with 21 possible values spaced at intervals of 0.05.

5.1.1 "Footsteps" Dataset

The algorithm for the generation of the "footsteps" dataset takes each of the 28 footsteps sound file, apply peak normalization at 0 dBFS, divides the audio file into

sections corresponding to each step and shuffle the order to generate 1000 different combinations of the same steps, resulting in 1000 sound file of 28 categories (each category corresponding to the sound file that originated the new file).

Figure 11: Representation of the “Footstep” dataset generation algorithm.

5.1.2 “Bees”, “Wind”, “Pistons”, “Applause” Dataset

The ‘Bees’, ‘Wind’, ‘Pistons’, and ‘Applause’ datasets are roughly imitative of: a group of bees buzzing and moving around in a small space, blowing wind, an 8-cycle engine, and applause varying in number of clappers and clapping rate, respectively. The controlling parameters for the generated audio are ‘busybodyFreqFactor’, ‘strength’, ‘rate_exp’, and ‘numClappers_exp’. The ‘busybodyFreqFactor’ controls the excursion of micro variations in pitch for the ‘Bees’ sound synthesis. The ‘strength’ parameter controls the average frequency around which the center frequency of a bandpass filter fluctuates for ‘Wind’ sound synthesis. The ‘rate_exp’ parameter controls the number of events per second for each piston in the ‘Pistons’ sound synthesis. Finally, the ‘numClappers_exp’ parameter controls the number of clapping persons per second for ‘Applause’ sound synthesis.

5.2 Dataset Tokenization

We tokenized the audio datasets through state-of-the-art Improved-RVQGAN Describe Audio Codec (DAC) via RVQ with 4 quantizers (corresponding to 4 code-books). The 44100 Hz RVQGAN model weights are used, matching the 44.1 kHz sample rate of the dataset sound files, without fine-tuning the original model. Each

sound file is pre-processed with zero-padding to obtain samples that are multiples of 512. Since 4 quantizers are used, each 512 samples of the sound file ("striding factor" in the DAC paper [7]) after encoding is, thus, represented by 4 discrete codes. Each of the codes is represented by indices ranging from 0 to 1023 (10 bits of information).

All the models presented use the "flattening" interleaved pattern, producing a 1D sequence of tokens. An offset algorithm is included to ensure that, during the inference phase, tokens of the generated sequence belong to the correct codebooks in order. By assigning a specific value range to each codebook, we can verify the correctness of the produced sequence by checking the value ranges in the predicted sequence. Moreover, RVQ is hierarchical, with the most important tokens belonging to the first quantizer and so on, ensuring no ambiguity in the modeling. This implies an increase in dictionary size and slower inference time, particularly due to the softmax operation at the end of the architecture. However, that compromise in inference time is not particularly relevant in relation to the computational complexity of the system (the impact is roughly linear), since the softmax operation is performed only once at the very end and not for each layer. Each audio file is thus transformed into sequences of integer numbers corresponding to indexes of the 4 codebooks of each quantizer. A special "starting token" is prepended to the sequence of each file.

Figure 12: Representation of the offset algorithm for the token IDs and a predicted sequence. Vocabulary size results in $4096 + \text{start token} = 4097$ unique tokens.

5.3 Generation Strategy

Self-attention mechanism allows the autoregressive Transformer network to attend a maximum number of tokens in input when computing the prediction of the next token in the sequence, that maximum number of tokens is defined as the “context” hyper-parameter. Generally speaking a larger “context” implies a more accurate next-token prediction, but at the cost of increasing computational complexity, since at each time step the whole previously predicted sequence is fed to the input of the Transformer.

Figure 13: Representation of the general autoregressive prediction mechanism for the models involved our research.

In procedural audio, leveraging self-attention on the entire sequence isn’t always ideal, as it can be computationally expensive. This is particularly true for audio signals with fixed statistical features, like texture or footstep sounds. For these types of sounds, a long context window often provides little benefit. Moreover, in a real-time conditioning scenario, it is beneficial to disregard predictions about parts of the sequence that were generated beyond a reasonable time interval in the past.

This reduces computational complexity and prevents potential bias from long-term structure. One such case could be footstep sound generation in the context of video game procedural audio, where it is advantageous to limit attention to no more than 5 or 6 seconds of sound. This prevents biasing future predictions based on long-term structure. A concrete example could be a situation where the user decides to abruptly change the conditioning of footsteps in real-time, such as switching from walking slowly to running very fast. In this particular situation, long-term information would degrade the influence of the real-time conditioning parameter. By focusing on recent context, the system can adapt quickly to new conditions without being influenced by outdated information. This ensures that real-time conditioning parameters have a more immediate and accurate effect on the generated audio.

For these reasons, for the models involved in our research, we experimented with relatively small context windows using either RoPE or learned positional encoding. Unlike sinusoidal positional encoding, which assigns a unique position vector to each position in the input sequence, RoPE preserves more information about the relative distances between positions. This is essential for capturing the relative positional relationships between tokens in a sequence, particularly in the scenario of real-time audio generation with a small context window.

5.4 Conditioning Strategies

Conditioning narrows down the space of possible outputs from the overall distribution of the dataset by imposing specific context information. This information restricts the model to generate outputs that are relevant to the provided context, thus limiting the possibilities compared to the broader, more varied outputs of unconditional synthesis. In procedural audio, the conditioning information runs in real-time and is common that takes the form of a lower-rate signal in comparison to the audio sample rate. In the context of this research, 4 different strategies to provide conditional information to the Transformer were explored: unconditional synthesis, “one-hot embedding injection” conditioning, “continues value embedding injection” conditioning, “control codes injection” conditioning.

In this research, conditioning is provided to the model as real-time signal at “striding factor” rate, and corresponds to the controlling parameter for the generated audio of the respective texture sound dataset (“busybodyFreqFactor” for “Bees”, “strength” for “Wind”, “rate_exp” for “Pistons”, “numClappers_exp” for “Applause”) and contact sound class for "Footsteps". This approach permits to interpolate in real-time between the parameters, even though in the datasets every sound has a fixed conditional parameter for the whole duration of the sound. Each conditioning signal for the textures can take 21 discrete values, ranging from 0.0 to 1.0 with intervals of 0.05 between each value. The conditioning signals for the "Footsteps" correspond to the 28 classes of footsteps sounds.

5.4.1 Unconditional Synthesis

Unconditional synthesis refers to generating data without any specific controlling condition. The model learns to generate samples from the overall distribution of the training data. During tokenization of the datasets, a special token (start token, ID: 4096) was added to the vocabulary and prepended at the beginning of every encoded audio file. Unconditional generation can be achieved by providing the start token as input to the Transformer.

5.4.2 “One-hot embedding injection” Conditioning

Inspired by previous studies [32] [33], we applied "latent code injection", a technique used in generative models, to introduce conditioning information into the model’s latent space. Our technique involves concatenating a one-hot encoded vector to the input embeddings.

One-hot encoding is a common method in data science and machine learning used to convert categorical data into a numerical format suitable for machine learning algorithms. In one-hot encoding, each category value in a feature is represented as a binary vector. This vector has a length equal to the number of unique categories in the feature, with all values set to zero except for the index representing the current category, which is set to one.

We treated numerical conditioning parameters as categorical data since discrete changes of adjacent values, in the specific case of our texture datasets, are small enough to not be distinguishable from continuous change. The one-hot vector of length $n_{categories}$ is concatenated to the $(d_{model} - n_{categories})$ learnable embedding vectors and frozen during training.

Figure 14: Representation of the “one-hot embedding injection” mechanism.

5.4.3 “Continuous value embedding injection” Conditioning

Our second strategy of "latent code injection," consists of directly concatenating the conditioning value to the input embeddings after mapping the value around 0. In practice, neural networks perform better when their weights hover around 0 and are equally balanced between positive and negative values. If this balance is not maintained, problems such as exploding gradients and unstable training often occur. To address this issue, a mapping algorithm is applied that uses a scalar offset to center the values around 0. As with the previous strategy, the conditioning part

of the embedding vector is frozen during training, so the conditioning parameter doesn't get updated. The advantage of this strategy is that it permits interpolation between discrete classes by feeding in numbers between those of two distinct classes.

Figure 15: Representation of the "Continuous value injection" mechanism.

5.4.4 “Control Codes Injection” Conditioning

Another strategy explored to condition the generation consists of injecting special tokens into the encoded token sequence. Special tokens are often used to instruct the model to generate content in a particular style, format, or domain. This method leverages the self-attention mechanism’s ability to be context-agnostic and efficiently handle sequences of multi-modal data. However, this process significantly increases the computational complexity, as it adds a new conditioning token every 4 tokens and enlarges the vocabulary size.

Figure 16: Representation of the “Control” codes injection mechanism.

Chapter 6

Experiments and Results

6.1 Models and Hyperparameters

This research involved training a total of 64 autoregressive decoder-only Transformer models across multiple datasets: 24 generative models from the "Footsteps" dataset, 14 from the "Bees" dataset, 8 from the "Applause" dataset, 9 from the "Wind" dataset, and 9 from the "Pistons" dataset. The study focused on several key hyperparameters: the number of layers, which determines the depth of the architecture; the number of heads, which affects the model's capacity to learn complex patterns; the block-size, which represents the duration of context considered by the model (set at 3 and 6 seconds); and the conditioning type and modality. These hyperparameters were varied to investigate their impact on model performance in terms of audio quality and inference time.

6.2 Training

Extensive experimentation across various datasets revealed that 100,000 training iterations were sufficient for all dataset and hyper-parameter combinations to reach a plateau in audio quality improvement for generated sequences that is no longer noticeable. The data loading consisted of 100,000 iterations, which involved training the Transformer on codes from 100,000 distinct sounds in chunks of block-size length randomly picked along the sound-file. For the 'footsteps' dataset, this number of iterations corresponded to more than three complete epochs, while for the other four texture datasets, it equated to over 15 full epochs. Considering the generation process of the "Footsteps" dataset, the ratio between the ambient and intrinsic dimensionality of the dataset is expected to be higher in relation to that of the texture datasets. This aspect is compensated for by a lower number of training epochs for the "Footsteps" dataset. Each model was trained using a dropout rate of 0.2, the AdamW optimizer with an adaptive learning rate ranging from 0.0001 to 0.003, and a batch size of 2. We split each dataset into 90% of data for training and 10% for validation. The training of all models was performed on an NVIDIA Tesla T4 GPU with 16 GB VRAM.

6.3 Quantitative Analysis

Inf. Time (s)	PE	Dataset	Train Loss	V.Loss	Ctx (s)	Emb. Size	NH	N. L	Cnd
278.21	RoPE	Footsteps	3.16	3.08	3	1024	8	4	sliding codes
117.34	RoPE	Footsteps	4.03	3.99	3	512	8	4	sliding
106.32	RoPE	Footsteps	3.6633	3.645	3	256	8	4	continuous
105.94	RoPE	Footsteps	3.96	3.94	3	128	8	4	sliding conditioning token
96.68	RoPE	Footsteps	3.96	3.94	3	64	8	4	sliding conditioning token
83.81	RoPE	Footsteps	4.84	4.92	3	128	8	4	sliding
82.85	RoPE	Footsteps	4.54	4.6	3	256	8	4	sliding
79.43	RoPE	Footsteps	5.17	5.22	3	64	8	4	sliding
50.08	RoPE	Footsteps	4.11	4.25	6	256	8	4	
46.69	learned	Footsteps	4.57	4.62	6	128	8	4	
46.58	RoPE	Footsteps	5.3313	5.331	3	36	8	2	fixed one-hot
45.26	RoPE	Footsteps	5.3313	5.331	3	36	8	2	fixed one-hot
42.36	RoPE	Footsteps	4.6888	4.7416	6	128	8	4	
41.97	RoPE	Footsteps	5.3313	5.331	3	36	8	2	fixed one-hot
41.88	RoPE	Footsteps	5.11	5.1044	6	64	8	4	
40.81	learned	Footsteps	3.97	4.06	6	256	8	4	
40.81	learned	Footsteps	5.06	5.0	6	64	8	4	
25.22	RoPE	Footsteps	5.1	5.12	6	64	8	2	
25.15	RoPE	Footsteps	4.42	4.45	6	256	8	2	
23.64	RoPE	Footsteps	4.8297	4.9321	6	128	8	2	
22.69	learned	Footsteps	4.81	4.73	6	128	8	2	
21.67	learned	Footsteps	4.12	4.21	6	256	8	2	
21.18	learned	Footsteps	5.11	5.06	6	64	8	2	
13.46	RoPE	Footsteps	4.87	4.92	6	128	2	2	
13.38	RoPE	Footsteps	4.47	4.43	6	256	2	2	
12.82	RoPE	Footsteps	5.14	5.21	6	64	2	2	
11.17	learned	Footsteps	4.78	4.86	6	128	2	2	
11.06	learned	Footsteps	4.33	4.34	6	256	2	2	
10.91	learned	Footsteps	5.11	5.13	6	64	2	2	
182.77	RoPE	Bees	1.97	1.98	3	511	8	2	codes
132.09	RoPE	Bees	2.09	2.14	3	491	8	2	one-hot changing
90.03	RoPE	Bees	2.34	2.35	3	255	8	2	continuous
87.09	RoPE	Bees	3.11	3.08	3	64	8	4	sliding
85.53	RoPE	Bees	2.86	2.84	3	127	8	2	continuous
84.68	RoPE	Bees	2.1566	2.1826	3	256	8	4	sliding
80.41	RoPE	Bees	2.56	2.52	3	128	8	4	sliding
66.66	RoPE	Bees	2.09	2.14	3	491	8	2	one-hot changing
46.3	RoPE	Bees	2.42	2.33	3	235	8	2	one-hot changing
45.59	RoPE	Bees	2.42	2.33	3	235	8	2	one-hot changing
45.38	RoPE	Bees	2.42	2.38	3	235	8	2	one-hot changing
45.15	RoPE	Bees	2.42	2.38	3	235	8	2	one-hot changing
44.52	RoPE	Bees	2.42	2.38	3	235	8	2	one-hot changing
43.91	RoPE	Bees	3.04	3.08	3	107	8	2	one-hot changing
164.67	RoPE	Applause	4.31	4.31	3	511	8	2	codes
129.44	RoPE	Applause	4.4	4.41	3	491	8	2	onehot changing
91.11	RoPE	Applause	4.68	4.69	3	127	8	2	continuous
89.65	RoPE	Applause	4.56	4.57	3	235	8	2	onehot changing
88.82	RoPE	Applause	4.9	4.89	3	107	8	2	onehot changing
81.58	RoPE	Applause	4.4634	4.4597	3	128	8	4	sliding
81.33	RoPE	Applause	4.4634	4.4597	3	128	8	4	sliding
81.09	RoPE	Applause	4.73	4.72	3	64	8	4	sliding
152.21	RoPE	Pistons	4.21	4.28	3	491	8	2	codes
100.19	RoPE	Pistons	4.34	4.24	3	511	8	2	continuous
93.13	RoPE	Pistons	4.3	4.25	3	255	8	2	continuous
90.32	RoPE	Pistons	4.43	4.38	3	235	8	2	onehot changing
89.07	RoPE	Pistons	4.96	4.84	3	107	8	2	onehot changing
88.58	RoPE	Pistons	4.16	4.17	3	256	8	4	sliding
87.63	RoPE	Pistons	4.69	4.56	3	127	8	2	continuous
85.66	RoPE	Pistons	4.2613	4.408	3	128	8	4	sliding
81.16	RoPE	Pistons	4.75	4.73	3	64	8	4	sliding
87.26	RoPE	Wind	4.33	4.32	3	127	8	2	continuous
88.5	RoPE	Wind	4.09	4.14	3	255	8	2	continuous
130.77	RoPE	Wind	4.06	4.05	3	511	8	2	continuous
80.1	RoPE	Wind	4.46	4.42	3	64	8	4	sliding
81.36	RoPE	Wind	4.11	4.13	3	128	8	4	sliding
85.93	RoPE	Wind	4.44	4.43	3	256	8	4	sliding
91.46	RoPE	Wind	4.39	4.39	3	107	8	2	onehot changing
94.19	RoPE	Wind	4.15	4.18	3	235	8	2	onehot changing
129.58	RoPE	Wind	8.24	8.23	3	491	8	2	onehot changing

Figure 17: Hyperparameters / Performance table comparison: “Inf. Time (s)” is the inference time measured with CPU, Apple MacBook Pro (2021) M1 macOS 13.5.2, Python 3.12.4. PE stands for Positional Encoding, Ctx (s) stands for Context window measured in seconds, Emb. Size corresponds to the number of learnable features for each embedding vector, NH stands for number of heads, N. L stands for number of layers, Cnd stands for conditioning type: “sliding codes” refers to real-time changing “Control Codes Injection” conditioning and “codes” for the fixed version, “sliding” refers to real-time changing “continuous value embedding injection” conditioning and “continuous” for the fixed version, “one-hot changing” refers to real-time changing “one hot embedding injection” and “fixed one-hot” for the fixed version.

The quantitative comparison of the models performance reveals intricate relationships between model architecture, dataset characteristics, and performance metrics. Embedding size emerges as a critical factor, significantly influencing both inference time and model accuracy, with larger embeddings generally yielding better accuracy at the cost of longer processing times. This trade-off between speed and accuracy is consistently observed across various configurations. The choice of position encoding method, predominantly RoPE, alongside the number of heads and layers, plays a crucial role in determining model performance, with RoPE models generally having longer inference times compared to learned embeddings. Dataset complexity appears to impact model behavior, with the "Footsteps" dataset showcasing the widest variability in results and the Bees dataset consistently outperforming other texture datasets in terms of lower loss. Context window size and specific conditioning strategies contribute to performance variations, although their precise impact remains inconclusive. The close proximity of train and validation loss values suggests good model generalization. While various conditioning strategies were employed, including "Control Codes Injection" which consistently increases inference time, their overall impact on performance was not immediately apparent. Notably, some configurations demonstrate consistent performance across datasets, yet the data underscores that optimal model design is highly context-dependent.

6.4 Qualitative Analysis

Two distinct types of artifacts significantly degrade audio quality and are easily noticeable when present. The first, which could be termed "Latent Step Frequency Artifact," manifests as a perceptible pitch corresponding to a fundamental frequency of approximately 86 Hz. This frequency precisely aligns with the codec's "latent step," which is equivalent to 512 samples. The second artifact presents as a voice-like noise, resulting from poor sequence modeling. Both of these artifacts can occur when the training process is insufficient, resulting in missed codes throughout the audio file. In particular both are highly correlated with the dimension of the embedding vectors.

It is noteworthy that any form of conditioning strategy acting on the embedding vectors tends to degrade audio quality to varying degrees, making these two artifacts more noticeable. Among the conditioning strategies, "control codes injection" yields the best audio quality, followed by "one-hot embedding injection" and "continuous value embedding injection." Fixed conditioning parameters result in less audio degradation compared to changing conditioning parameters. There is no evident correlation between the resulting subjective audio quality and the training and validation losses, although differences become noticeable at extreme values. Reducing the number of heads to fewer than 8 notably degrades audio quality.

The dimension of the embedding vectors parameter has the most significant impact on audio quality, followed by the number of layers and context window size. With a d_{model} parameter of 256 or higher, 4 or more layers, and the use of RoPE (Rotary Position Embedding), the resulting audio quality matches that of the original dataset even if the conditioning strategies are applied for each of the datasets considered in this research.

Chapter 7

Discussion and Conclusion

7.1 Interpretation of the Results

The purpose of this research was to demonstrate strategies that overcome the limitations of Neural Audio Synthesis (NAS) approaches in terms of conditioning. We showed that codec-based audio language modeling is a promising approach for procedural audio, both for its conditioning possibilities and the high quality of the sounds it produces.

Previous state-of-the-art review [1] in procedural audio claimed that neural approaches have "limited" control over "meaningful" conditioning parameters. However, our exploration of three strategies, with appropriate hyperparameters, achieved both high audio quality and "meaningful" conditioning parameters, contradicting this assertion.

Furthermore, prior research [2][3][4] has highlighted the need for audio models of "environmental sounds" (non-speech, non-music sounds), as the majority of research in codec-based audio language modeling focuses on music and speech. Our study addresses this gap by exploring models for "environmental sounds," specifically investigating the current possibilities of codec-based audio language modeling for the subcategories of "texture sounds" and "contact sounds."

Embedding size and number of heads emerge as pivotal factors, significantly influencing both inference time, model accuracy and sound quality. This research reveals a consistent trade-off between speed and accuracy across various configurations, with larger embeddings generally yielding better accuracy at the cost of increased processing time. Position encoding methods, particularly RoPE, along with the number of heads and layers, crucially impact model performance. Dataset complexity notably affects model behavior, with the "Footsteps" dataset exhibiting the widest variability and the "Bees" dataset consistently outperforming other texture datasets in terms of lower loss.

While various conditioning strategies were explored, their overall impact on performance was not immediately apparent, though "Control Codes Injection" consistently increased inference time. This research identified two distinct types of artifacts that significantly degrade audio quality: the "Latent Step Frequency Artifact" and a voice-like noise resulting from poor sequence modeling. These findings underscore the critical role of embedding vector dimensions and sufficient training in mitigating such artifacts.

The study concludes that optimal model design is context-dependent, with the dimension of embedding vectors, number of layers, and context window size having the most significant impact on audio quality. In practice, with a d_{model} parameter of 256 or higher, 4 or more layers, and the use of RoPE, the resulting audio quality matches that of the original dataset across all examined datasets, even with applied conditioning strategies.

7.2 Future Work

This research did not set out to conduct a systematic study on the performance of the generative models and conditioning strategies considered. As a result, the comparison leans towards certain types of hyperparameters, sounds, and conditioning strategies. Instead, the approach was exploratory in nature. When particular patterns emerged in the generated audio files, or when the expected sound quality was not achieved with certain hyperparameters, models were trained with adjusted settings. This iterative process guided the exploration rather than a comprehensive, systematic evaluation. We leave a systematic analysis with balanced representation of models across different hyperparameter configurations as future work.

The author's subjective qualitative evaluation falls short of providing definitive conclusions. A more comprehensive approach would involve a systematic subjective qualitative evaluation with numerous human participants, yielding more reliable results. Incorporating objective metrics would also enhance the overall assessment.

Procedural audio requires real-time performance, and the Python prototypes presented in this work are insufficient for measuring this aspect. Therefore, implementation in a faster programming language (such as C++ or Rust) is necessary for a comprehensive evaluation.

List of Figures

1	VQ-VAE vector quantization process from [10].	5
2	EnCodec architecture from [13].	6
3	Transformer architecture from [3].	9
4	Token embedding mechanism representation.	11
5	Self-attention mechanism representation for one head.	14
6	Fig. 1. Timeline of current neural codec models and codec-based audio language models from [27].	15
7	JukeBox encoding, decoding and RVQ process from the original paper [28].	16
8	MusicGen different codebook interleaving patterns from the original paper [2].	17
9	Stack and delay codebook pattern from [29].	18
10	Multi-Scale Transformer representation from [9]. $\langle e \rangle$ represent the end of the sequence. z_t^k denotes the k-th audio token at t-th frame.	19
11	Representation of the “Footstep” dataset generation algorithm.	21
12	Representation of the offset algorithm for the token IDs and a predicted sequence. Vocabulary size results in $4096 + \text{start token} = 4097$ unique tokens.	22
13	Representation of the general autoregressive prediction mechanism for the models involved our research.	23
14	Representation of the “one-hot embedding injection” mechanism.	26
15	Representation of the “Continuous value injection” mechanism.	27
16	Representation of the “Control” codes injection mechanism.	28

- 17 Hyperparameters / Performance table comparison: “Inf. Time (s)” is the inference time measured with CPU, Apple MacBook Pro (2021) M1 macOS 13.5.2, Python 3.12.4. PE stands for Positional Encoding, Ctx (s) stands for Context window measured in seconds, Emb. Size corresponds to the number of learnable features for each embedding vector, NH stands for number of heads, N. L stands for number of layers, Cnd stands for conditioning type: “sliding codes” refers to real-time changing “Control Codes Injection” conditioning and “codes” for the fixed version, “sliding” refers to real-time changing “continuous value embedding injection“ conditioning and “continuous” for the fixed version, “one-hot changing” refers to real-time changing “one hot embedding injection” and “fixed one-hot” for the fixed version. 31

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